

S1 Table. Back-transformed model-predicted means, SE, and 95% CI for all outcomes scored, along with model outputs

Back-transformed model predicted means (obtained using type="response" in emmeans in R) and CI:

Behavior	Control		Pipe		Bucket	
	Emmeans (SE)	95% CI	Emmeans (SE)	95% CI	Emmeans (SE)	95% CI
Latency to eat TMR (s)	60.2 (15.7)	[39.0,131.4]	38.4 (10.6)	[24.4,90.3]	4.6 (1.3)	[2.9,10.8]
Proportion of time spent eating TMR	0.57 (0.06)	[0.45, 0.69]	0.38 (0.06)	[0.26,0.50]	0.26 (0.06)	[0.15,0.36]
TMR consumed (g)	44.7 (9.9)	[30.7,82.3]	30.9 (6.8)	[21.2,56.8]	56.0 (13.1)	[37.7,108.5]

Model results:

Pairwise comparisons and p-values are only presented if the overall effect is significant

Behavior	Model type	Anova (Type II SS)		
		DF	chisq	p-value
Latency to eat TMR	Generalized linear model	2,22	35.525	<0.001
Control v. Bucket		-	-	0.008
Control v. Pipe		-	-	0.511
Bucket v. Pipe		-	-	0.012
Proportion of time spent eating TMR	Betaregression	2,21	12.952	0.002
Control v. Bucket		-	-	<0.001
Control v. Pipe		-	-	0.070
Bucket v. Pipe		-	-	0.300
TMR consumed	Generalized linear model	2,23	3.450	0.178

Chi-square data + model results:

Behavior	Control # of calves	Pipe # of calves	Bucket # of calves	DF	X-squared	p-value
Startles, flinches, retreats	9 (100%)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)	2	11.213	0.004
Lying down	2 (25%)	6 (75%)	4 (50%)	2	4.000	0.135